

Membrane potential based assay for SLC15A2 using HEK-293 SLC15A2 OE cells

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Assay description

FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, upon activation of SLC15A2. The assay allows the detection of ion channel and transporter modulation by increasing or decreasing the fluorescent signal as cellular membrane potential changes. When cells are depolarized dye enters the cells, causing an increase in fluorescent signal, conversely, cells hyperpolarization results in dye exit and decreased fluorescence (Figure 1).

SLC15A2 belongs to the proton-coupled oligopeptide transporters (POTs) family, it is an electrogenic transporter that mediates the cellular uptake of di/tripeptides and many peptide-like drugs such as cefadroxil, valacyclovir and others, utilizing an inwardly directed proton gradient.

Figure 1. Principal of a FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye assay. The assay measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, consequence of channels and transporters modulation. The fluorescent signal increases in intensity during membrane depolarization as dye follows the positively charged ions inside the cell. During membrane hyperpolarization, fluorescent signal decreases in intensity as dye follows the positively charged ions out of the cell.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC15A2 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 5'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 48 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂. The day after cells were induced with 1 µg/mL Doxycycline (not induced and mock control in parallel).

Membrane Potential assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated 30 minutes at RT in 20 µL/well of FMP-Blue-Dye (0.5X dye dissolved in Tyrode's Buffer pH 7.4 containing HEPES/MES as indicated in the manufacturer manual) and plates analysed at FLIPR^{TETRA} reader using a λ_{exc} 510 - 545nm / λ_{em} 565 - 625 nm filter.

To test pharmacology 20 µL/well of substrates: Gly-Sar (2X in Tyrode's buffer HEPES/MES at pH 7.4, as well as in Tyrode's buffer HEPES/MES supplied with 8 mM (2X) HCl to reach a final concentration of 4 mM HCl and a final pH of 6.8 after injection), starting from 3 mM, semi-log dilution steps (8 concentrations, only buffer included); L-carnosine (2X in Tyrode's buffer HEPES/MES at pH 7.4, as well as in Tyrode's buffer HEPES/MES supplied with 8 mM (2X) HCl to reach a final concentration of 4 mM HCl and a final pH of 6.8 after injection), starting from 3 mM, semi-log dilution steps (8 concentrations, only buffer included) were online injected at the plate reader and fluorescence recorded.

Data analysis

FLIPR^{TETRA} measurements obtained from different well replicates were analysed by using the Screenworks software (Molecular Devices, Version 3.0.1.4). Absolute Response (RFU) is obtained applying "Subtract Bias on Sample: n" (where n = Timepoint of compound injection) whereas Assay Window Response ($\Delta F/F_0$) is obtained applying "Response over Baseline" correction (where Baseline = Timepoint -1 and -2 before activator injection) and "Background Subtraction". Data were then exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC). Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create

sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC50/IC50 values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 6).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC15A2
Synonyms	Peptide Transporter 2, PEPT2
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 15 (Oligopeptide Transporter)
UniProt ID	Q16348
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE0251-6 (HEK-SLC15A2-WTOE-p5-6)

Assay data

	Compound name (1)	Gly-Sar
	PubChem CID	93131
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, # G3127
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 123 μM at pH 7.4; 39 μM at pH 6.8
	Compound name (2)	L-Carnosine
	PubChem CID	439224
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, # C9625
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type	EC ₅₀ = 28 μM at pH 6.8

	(i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	
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Discussion

The Membrane Potential Assay for SLC15A2 showed a specific and dose-dependent fluorescent signal increase upon injection of Gly-Sar and L-Carnosine. The increase in the fluorescence intensity is a result of cell depolarization that reflects the co-transport of H⁺ through the transporter together with the substrate. Better results were obtained using a more acidic pH (pH 6.8).

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).